

Extended abstract

Title: Are Digital Innovation Policies Effective in Promoting the Development of Digital Economy in China?

How latecomers of emerging countries catch up with the incumbents on technological innovation is always an important topic (Guo et al., 2021). China is also facing challenges in upgrading its manufacturing value-added in the global market and transferring to a more sustainable economic growth model. As digital innovation is advanced more than any other technological innovation in human history, it has become the driving force of Chinese economic growth and transition (Gimpel & Röglinger, 2015; Li et al., 2022; Michael Fitzgerald et al., 2014). Digital innovation has characteristics of convergency and generativity, allowing digital technology to lead to more distributed innovation, combinational innovation, and digital platforms (Mention, 2019). In 2013, the size of the digital economy was about 9.5 trillion, accounting for 20.3% of China's GDP. In 2020, the size already increased to around 39.2 trillion, taking a share of 38.6% of GDP. China is also a leading digital economy in the global market. According to CGTN (2022), the size of China's digital economy is ranking second in the world in 2020.

As the Chinese government plays a predominant role in affecting the digital economy. China has developed national strategies for the digital economy in its Medium to Long-term Planning for Scientific and Technological Development plans. For example, in Fourteenth Five-Year Plan Outline, the Chinese government has proposed accelerating digital development and building a Digital China(Xinhuanet, 2022). In response to the government's national strategy, the Chinese government has introduced more policies for the digital economy. The data from the Bailu Zhiku policy database shows that, in 2013, the Chinese government introduced 342 digital innovation policies, and in 2021, the Chinese government introduced 1242 digital innovation policies. The figures have tripled in the past eight years. Although the Chinese government has implemented a series of innovation policies to stimulate digital innovation in different regions of China, existing studies may not systematically evaluate and compare the effectiveness of these policies in fostering digitalization in China. Some scholars prove that a specific policy is effective. For example, Chen & Yang (2019) found that the R&D

tax credit policy has a significant positive impact on a firm's innovation output. Liu et al. (2016) found that R&D subsidies can significantly stimulate a firm's business R&D and R&D intensity. Guan & Yam (2015) compared the effects of loans, tax credits, and direct subsidies on innovation performance and concluded that special loans and tax credits positively influence innovative economic performance. Some studies have opposite conclusions: the government innovation policy may curb innovation. Boeing (2016) found that R&D subsidies have a crowding-out effect on firms' business R&D investment in the earlier periods. Belitski et al. (2019) proved that the training and skills for innovation gain lower returns of innovation outcomes before times of crisis. Guan & Yam (2015) demonstrated that government direct financial subsidies sometimes even harm innovation economic performance. At the same time, some studies found an inverted U-shaped relationship between University-Industry collaboration policy and knowledge output and achievement transformation in the innovation chain (Cheng et al., 2018). The current understanding of the effectiveness of innovation policies is still ambiguous, and the government may waste many valuable resources on policies that are not very effective. Therefore, it is important to find out how the Chinese government uses policy instrument mix to promote the development of the digital economy and comprehensively evaluate the policy effectiveness of digital innovation. Thus, the research questions of this paper are as follows:

Research Question 1: "What kind of policy instruments are frequently used by the Chinese government to promote the digital economy?"

Research Question 2: "Is every type of policy instrument effective in boosting the digital economy?"

Research Question 3: "Among all applied policy instruments, which policy instruments are more effective in facilitating the digital economy?"

The unit of analysis is a province (excluding Hong Kong, Macaw, and Taiwan). This study will collect two kinds of data. The first is the 2013-2021 digital innovation policy document at the province level, collected from Bailu Zhiku (<http://www.bailuzhiku.com/>) by a web's crawler. The second is the 2020 digital economy index by provinces, collected from the microdatas.cn

database. The approach of Natural Language Processing will be used to clean and process the collected policy documents. In this process, some Chinese keywords ("税收减免 Tax deduction," "孵化器 Incubators," "政府采购 Procurement," and "补贴 Subsidy" etc.) will be used to identify the policy instruments in the policy text. Based on the innovation policy instrument framework proposed by Elder et al. (Elder et al. 2016), we define thirteen types of instruments in this study, including "R&D tax credits," "Direct R&D support," "Training and skills," "Entrepreneurship," "Technical services and advice," "Cluster," "Collaboration," "Innovation network," "Procurement," "Innovation prizes," "Standard," "Regulations," "Technology foresight." This study will also construct a multivariate regression model to test if a certain innovation policy instrument significantly impacts the digital economy development of provinces in China and compare the effectiveness of different innovation policies.

The preliminary results show a huge regional heterogeneity of digital innovation development in China. Coastal regions like "Guangdong" (N=302), "Zhejiang" (N=193), "Jiangsu" (N=188), "Fujian" (N=165), "Shandong" (N=128), "Beijing" (N=100), "Tianjin" (N=85) and "Shanghai" (N=73) have launched more digital innovation policies. Southern provinces pay more attention to digital innovation than northern provinces (Guangdong, Zhejiang, Jiangsu, and Fujian compares to Shandong, Beijing, and Tianjin). Besides, Chinese governments frequently use direct support for R&D and innovation, training and skills, and cluster policy when developing a digital economy. Lastly, from the multivariate regression results, we observe that both demand ($\beta=12.57$, $p<0.05$) and supply policies ($\lambda=2.62$, $p<0.05$) can significantly improve the development of the digital economy development and the demand-side policy is more effective than the supply-side policy.

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